

Linguadidactic problems of teaching foreign languages in the system of continuous education. (schools, lyceums and colleges)

Plan

1. Common European Framework of Reference.
2. Teaching and learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan.
3. Foreign language as an educational subject.
4. Teaching foreign languages in the world and in Uzbekistan.
5. Principles, goals and content of TFL-s.

Key words: *CEFR document, framework, Reference levels, State Educational Standard, principles, goals, content of TFL, language skills, language material, linguistic material, vocabulary, grammar, phonological minima.*

Document of «Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment»

The document of «Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment» (CEFR) was created by the Council of Europe.

The CEFR document is the result of a need for a common international framework for language learning facilitated cooperation among educational institutions in different countries. It was demanded to create a single and integrated educational space in Modern languages¹ teaching/learning and international standards of language assessment in European countries. The main function of this document was to provide a common basis for the elaboration of language syllabuses, curricula, guidelines, examination, and coursebooks across Europe. It also provided a method of assessing and teaching which was applied to all Modern languages in Europe.

Under the CEFR learning language proposes during a whole life as dynamic progression through all levels. That's why the aim of the CEFR is to designate standards to be reached to subsequent stages of teaching and learning Modern languages. This document has been accepted as a standard framework to be implemented also in many other countries, i.e. in every language teaching and learning context. The CEFR has been translated into at least 37 languages. The implication of this Framework in different countries is reflected in the development of National Curricula or State Educational Standards of FL.

The CEFR document enhances the transparency of courses, syllabuses and qualifications, thus promoting international cooperation in the field of Modern languages which requires mutual recognition of qualifications gained in different learning contexts and aids to promote students' mobility.

According to the CEFR, learners of every LT context should be facilitated to gain the particular proficiency level in a particular stage of learning.

In the CEFR the cultural context is observed in the language setting. Cultural context proposes taking into consideration the specificity of national condition of teaching and learning Modern languages, and the national-cultural features of the adjoined languages (learned and native languages).

Learning Modern languages through a whole life proposes six common reference levels of education:

C 2	Mastery Effective Operational Proficiency	Proficient user
B 2 B 1	Vantage Threshold	Independent user
A 1 A 2	Waystage Breakthrough	Basic user

Acquiring each stage successively learners have real opportunity to communicate with people of other language contexts.

Descriptors in the CEFR

In the CEFR document the reference of six levels is given and designed as illustrative descriptors (scales) in the term of «Can Do» statements from level A1 to C2. These scales can be used as a tool for comparing levels of ability amongst learners of FL and also offer «a means to map the progress» of learners². The descriptors are built to do two dimensions: 1) through a vertical dimension we see a progression through all levels; 2) through a horizontal dimension the different context of teaching and learning are presented. The common reference levels of CEFR³ are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Common Reference Levels (global)

C2 - Can understand with ease virtually everything heard or read. Can summarize information from different spoken and written sources, reconstructing arguments and accounts in a coherent presentation. Can express him/herself spontaneously, very fluently and precisely, differentiating finer shades of meaning even in more complex situations.

C1 - Can understand a wide range of demanding, longer texts, and recognize implicit meaning. Can express him/her fluently and spontaneously without much obvious searching for expressions. Can use language flexibly and effectively for social, academic and professional purposes. Can produce clear, well-structured, detailed text on complex subjects, showing controlled use of organizational patterns, connectors and cohesive devices.

B2- Can understand the main ideas of complex texts on both concrete and abstract topics, including technical discussions in his/her field of specialization. Can interact with a degree of fluency and spontaneity that makes regular interaction with native speakers quite possible without strain for either party. Can produce clear, detailed text on a wide range of subjects and explain a viewpoint on a topical issue giving the advantages and disadvantages of various options.

B1- Can understand the main points of clear standard input on familiar matters regularly encountered in work, school, leisure, etc. Can deal with most situations likely to arise whilst travelling in an area where the language is spoken. Can produce simple connected texts on topics which are familiar or of personal interest. Can describe experiences and events, dreams, hopes & ambitions and briefly give reasons and explanations for opinions and plans.

A2- Can understand sentences and frequently used expressions related to areas of most immediate relevance (e.g. very basic personal and family information, shopping, local geography, employment). Can communicate in simple and routine tasks requiring a simple and direct exchange of information on familiar and routine matters.

Can describe in simple terms aspects of his/her background, immediate environment and matters in areas of immediate need.

A1- Can understand and use familiar everyday expressions and very basic phrases aimed at the satisfaction of needs of a concrete type. Can introduce him/herself and others and can ask and answer questions about personal details such as where he/she lives, people he/she knows and things he/she has. Can interact in a simple way provided the other person talks slowly and clearly and is prepared to help.

The scales given in the table are global and they are not exhaustive, because they are not taking into consideration every context of language use. The CEFR describes language learners' ability in terms of «speaking, listening, reading and writing» at six reference levels. The reference levels of FL are examined through communicative tasks and activities.

For national educational system the illustrated descriptors in CEFR are adapted or created with fitting the learned language, cultural context and a certain set of competences. Under the CEFR the result of LT is shown through a performance of a certain level of communicative competence

(proficiency). The ways how to use a language for communication and what knowledge and skills should be developed are stated thoroughly in this framework.

The Decree of President Islam Karimov «On measures for further improvement of foreign languages learning» (December 10, 2012)⁵ is a key factor for modernization of teaching foreign languages at all stages, in which the importance of teaching and learning English across the country were pointed out. Taking account this derivative document the competence-based teaching was implemented in the Uzbekistan system of FLT.

This approach is an educational movement that refers to the outcomes of learning in the development of language programs and language skills of students. The essence of this approach is a new content-based on forming and developing a set of learners' competences. The process of acquiring this content brings action-oriented character. Language use, embracing language learning, comprises the actions performed by learners who as individuals and as social agents develop a range of competences, both general and particular all components of the communicative competence. The core of this approach is interpreted as students draw on the competences at their disposal in various contexts under various conditions and under various constraints to engage in language activities involving language processes to produce and/or receive texts in relation to themes in specific domains, activating those strategies which seem most appropriate for carrying out the tasks to be accomplished⁶. The monitoring of these actions by the participants leads to the reinforcement or modification of their competences.

The main feature of this approach is orientation to results of FLT/L fixed in the State Educational Standard. For this purpose descriptors what the learners should know and can be put on the curriculum in the result are worked out.

In Uzbekistan ELT is seen as a career in a field of educational specialization: it requires a specialized knowledge base obtained through both academic study and practical experience. Nowadays the demonstration of a certain level of proficiency in English as component of certification is required.

In Uzbekistan the multistage model of FLT has been worked out on the basis of continuous, succession, taking into consideration the international standards, and localization of EL teaching and learning methodology and materials (adapting to the national context). It is related to the well-known multilevel model of FLT in the foreign countries.

It is very important for teachers to identify ways to best represent local culture and explain non-native elements. Besides it is necessary to use humanizing material as activities which help to make the language learning process a more affective experience and finding ways of helping the learners

to connect “what is in the book to what is in their minds”⁴. Thus, it is necessary to humanize the teaching materials.

In Uzbekistan authors of syllabuses, curricula, coursebooks and other guides try to humanize materials, present materials in real-life and culturally familiar language contexts and match the language instructions with students needs and personal preferences. All this allows expressing learners' identity and empowers them to make a decision about what they need to learn.

The effectiveness of teachers' pedagogical activity, at first, depends on acquiring the ideas of modernization. A modernization means: 1) changing the goal and results of education; application of modern methods and technologies in practice of teaching/learning; reworking out the state standards and curricula for EL teaching and learning. Thus, all components of methodical system of ELT should be modernized, particularly:

- 1) approaches and principles to EL teaching and learning;
- 2) goals of teaching and learning;
- 3) content of EL teaching and learning;
- 4) aids, methods and techniques;
- 5) ways and forms of control of the results of EL teaching and learning.

In our conditions the CEFR is used for development of the language policy to set minimum language requirements for a wide range of purposes, in curriculum planning, preparing coursebooks and development of methods of teaching and tools of evaluation. It is intended for dynamic progress in acquiring FL.

Within this scope, the efforts of teachers and learners at all levels of education are encouraged and supported by developing appropriate methods and teaching materials, appropriate forms and instruments for the evaluating of learning programs. «Research and development programs leading to the introduction, at all educational levels, of methods and materials best suited to enabling different classes and types of student are promoted to acquire a communicative proficiency appropriate to their specific needs»⁵. So in obtaining a communicative proficiency the importance of methods and teaching materials play an important role.

The modern model of teaching and learning English in Uzbekistan.

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Practical and cultural goals of EL teaching and learning

The students mastering FL as means of communication should be able to use the language in the oral and written forms of speech. The requirements for practical mastery in language subskills (pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar) and skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) are represented in the curriculum and syllabus for every stage. The State educational standard stresses that the learners should have a communicative competence which presupposes an adequate proficiency in a FL as a means of communication, instruction and independent learning.

Finally, practical aims encompass certain volumes of language material: phonetic, lexical and grammatical items. Some of this material is subject to

reproductive assimilation, some - to **perceptive; these are also known as active and passive language material.**

The goal envisages a guideline, i.e. strategy of teaching and is accomplished during solving of a number of specific tasks which act as tactics. They determine the learners activities, their work with basic and ancillary means of instruction, inculcation of sub-skills (phonetic, grammatical, lexical, orthographic, etc.) and ability to understand English, to read aloud and silently, and to speak within a set range of situations.

It should be mentioned that the achievement of practical goals in FLT makes possible the realization of educational, cultural and developmental ones.

So, learning a FL is understood as a goal and as a means of instruction with clear-cut, short, interim and ultimate objectives, rational planning of all types of activity with special emphasis on communicative competence at all levels of teaching/learning.

As we know educational and cultural developments go together.

Cultural goal makes a substantial contribution:

- to developing pupils' linguistic outlook, as they get acquainted with some phenomena which are not typical of their mother-tongue (e.g. tenses, articles, EL word order);
- to developing pupils' communicative abilities;
- to widening pupils' communicative vision of the world, as it enables them to get acquainted with the life, customs and traditions of the people whose language they study;
- to developing pupils' intellect, their voluntary and involuntary memory, their imaginative abilities, logical thinking, etc.

The cultural goal is achieved within:

- the critical, patient and creative attitude to oneself and others, to a new culture, event, knowledge;
- the development of different character traits, outlooks, beliefs, moral-esthetic and emotional experience, different kinds of motivation and the abilities to use them to contribute successfully into the process of real and pedagogical communication;
- the development of the awareness of the new activities, new people civilizations;
- the development of the desire to cooperate and socialize;
- the keeping cultural traditions of one's own country and understanding and respect others'; to compare different cultures, to express a personal point of view on other cultures, problems as well as to use the knowledge obtained from other subjects.
- It is important to point out and note down that cultural goals are realized within the process of achieving practical objectives.

Educational and developmental goals of EL teaching and learning

The practical and cultural goals are closely connected with the educational one because FLL advances moral and aesthetic education. Teachers and methodologists pay much attention to educational capacities in the teaching and learning process. Of

great importance is the linguistic aspect - the contextual side of the material in the foreign language: texts, exercises, ostensive and audio-visual materials used in the classroom, outside school hours, and independent learning.

The goal of education is to develop individuals who adhere to definite moral principles, value knowledge and learning, can and will be able to think and find out things for themselves.

Learning, as we know, is a function of the total involvement and is the result of interactive process with students and teachers having an influence on the outcomes of such interaction. Thus, learning a FL adds to the learners' mental powers, sharpens their wits, develops their intelligence and contributes to their general outlook.

Classroom language experiences should be functional. Language use and study should fulfill purposes that are meaningful and obvious to pupils. Repeated interaction with classical literature also increases pupils' sensitivity to social, cultural dynamics and to the emotional needs of others. The teacher's role and attitude should be consistent with educational goals. "Consistency" here is one of trusting, i.e. respecting students' opinions and desires towards fairness. The "consistency" here is between having a rule and applying it in the same manner with all people including one's own.

The educational goals can be achieved by means of:

- selection of language material;
- successful organization and conduction of the English language lesson and an effective combination of its main components;
- choice of visual aids;
- the teacher's manners and appearance;
- teaching learners to work with books on their own, i.e. independently.

The **developmental goal** of teaching the English language is recently admitted as a scientific category in methodology of FLT. However, it is very difficult to find relevant instructional materials related to this goal. There is brief information about the developmental goal in the book written by G.V. Rogova and I.N. Vereshagina.

The main idea of the developmental goal is how to teach a learner:

- to develop the learners' creativity, intellectual and cognitive abilities;
- to develop different types of memory (visual/audio, short/long-termed, voluntary/involuntary), attention, skills, necessary for creative activities;
- to develop mechanisms of anticipation, predicting, guessing, etc.;
- to develop the learners' initiative, logical thinking. These are abilities concerning to start, to go on and to finish their communication.

Learning a FL leads to new horizons of linguistic competence where graphic, phonetic, lexical and grammatical items come into play. Such learning develops logical thinking of the learners because knowledge acquisition is related to such categories as analysis, synthesis, comparison, deduction, and others. This process is also related to the work of the aural, visual, kinesthetic, and motor analyzers aspects. They have a direct impact on the development of memory as the learners have to memorize lists of words, word-combinations, phrases, models of sentence building as well as their use in communication.

Books, textbooks offer ample opportunities to develop pupils' Gnostic abilities.

They learn a lot of interesting things about the countries, cities, events, historical places, schools, traditions, holidays and famous people (statesmen, public figures, and travelers), etc.

A well-organized, purposeful activity guided by the teachers and performed independently can ensure motivation - a positive interest, a desire and a greater willingness to learn a FL.

The developmental goal proposes developing of language intuition, language guessing, memory, logics (analysis, synthesis, comparison, sensory perception, motivational sphere, communicative skills; individual qualities such as hardworking, will, purposefulness, and activity).

Content of FLT

The first component is habits and skills which pupils should acquire (listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing).

The second component is a linguistic one. It includes:

1. Language material (sentence – patterns, pattern – dialogues, texts)
2. Linguistic material, i.e. phonology, grammar and vocabulary
3. The third component – methodological component, i.e. the techniques which pupils should acquire to learn the FL in a most effective way. The content of teaching is laid down in the syllabus and realized in teaching materials and in the teacher's own speech.

The content of foreign language teaching or what to teach is one of the main problems the Methods deals with. In this chapter an attempt is made to touch on the chief components which, we think, should constitute the content of foreign language teaching in schools; a more detailed consideration will be given in appropriate chapters dealing with teaching various aspects of the language and language skills.

The first component of "what to teach" is habits and skills which pupils should acquire while learning a foreign language. According to the aims of learning this subject they are: hearing (listening comprehension), speaking, reading, and writing. The level of habits and skills is determined by the syllabus for each form. However, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of skills, or the so-called terminal behaviour, is not defined yet for different types of schools and stages of instruction. This is one of the problems for methodologists to investigate and solve. Nevertheless, some attempts have been made in this respect. Thus in school syllabi we can find some directions as to the level of skills that should be reached in each particular form and their development from form to form. For example, the requirements for hearing and reading skills differ in the 9th and 10th forms. In the 9th form pupils should be able to understand oral language on the basis of the material previously learned and within the topics covered, while in the 10th form the material for hearing should include 1—2 unfamiliar words for pupils to guess their meaning, and to understand a text received by ear, based on the material learned and on a topic close to those pupils have worked at. This is a new "qualitative step" for pupils in understanding oral language. If in the 9th form

pupils should read with the speed of 1 000 signs per academic hour, in the 10th form the speed of reading is 1 300.'

The second component of "what to teach" is language (textual) material, arranged in topics and serving as starting points for the development of oral language and written language, which allows the teacher to reach the practical, educational, and cultural aims set by the syllabus.

For example, in the junior stage (the 5th and 6th forms) pupils should speak and read about school, home, town and countryside, nature, physical training and sports. In the senior stage the textual material should cover the following topics: the life of the youth in Uzbekistan and abroad; sport in Uzbekistan and abroad; industry, agriculture, and science in Uzbekistan and abroad; history and geography of the country whose language pupils study; art and literature in Uzbekistan and abroad.² Topics for speaking and reading are developed from form to form, i. e., the pupil's ability to read and speak on a certain topic is widened as his vocabulary and grammar are enriched.

The third component of the content of foreign language teaching is linguistic material, i. e., phonology, grammar, and vocabulary carefully selected for the purpose. The selection of linguistic material, the compiling of the so-called minima, for instance, minimum vocabulary and minimum grammar, has always been one of the most important and difficult problems to be solved and, although a great deal of work has been done in this respect,⁴ we are still on the way to its solution. A limited body of linguistic material is required by pupils who have about 600 class hours at their disposal spread over six years (extensive course), and at the same time it must be large enough to serve as a sound basis for developing pupils' language skills.

To sum up what has been said above, the content of foreign language teaching involves:

- 1) language skills: hearing, speaking, reading, and writing;
- 2) language (textual) material;
- 3) linguistic material; vocabulary; grammar, phonological minima.

In conclusion it should be said that the content of teaching in our schools is laid down in the syllabus and realized in teaching materials and in the teacher's own speech.

What to teach or the content of foreign language teaching is one of the main problems the Methods deals with.

The following component constitute the content of foreign language teaching in schools Instruction in a foreign language comprises ,like instruction in other school subjects (a) the imparting of knowledge, (b) the formation of habits, and (c) the development skills.

The first component of "what to teach" (content) is habits and skills which pupils should acquire while learning a foreign language. Habits are series of connected acts which have become automatic or semi - automatic as the result of repetitions.

Skills - are combination of specific useful habits, serving a definite purpose and requiring the application of definite knowledge.

The four basic skills to be acquired as the result of the study of a foreign language they are the ability to understand the language when heard, to speak it, to read it, and to write it. In other words they are hearing (language comprehension), speaking, reading, and writing. The level of habits and skills is determined by the syllabus for each form.

The second component of “what to teach” is a linguistic one. It includes on the one hand ,language material, such as sentence patterns, utterance - patterns, pattern-dialogues, text different in style arranged in topic and serving as starting points for the development of oral language and written language, which allows the teacher to reach the practical educational, and cultural aims set by the syllabys. For example, in the junior stage (4x5 forms) pupils should speak and read about school, home, town and countryside, nature, psychical training and sports.

The third component of what “what to teach” is a methodological component i.e. pupils should be taught how to learn the foreign language, how to work at he subject to attain the aims. To sum up, the content of foreign language teaching involves three main components:

1.Psychological components: habits and skills which ensure the use of the target language as a means of communication in oral (hearing, speaking) and written (reading, writing) forms.

2.Linguistic components i.e. language and linguistic material which should be assimilated to be used in language skills.

3.Methodological component i.e. the techniques which pupils should acquire to learn the foreign language in a most effective way.

Consequently, the dichotomy between language and speech plays an important role in FLT. Language is a system of signs and speech is a manifestation of this language system in concrete communicative acts. Both language and speech make up two sides of the same phenomenon, one whole, and at the same time each of them has specific units.

Language units include phonemes, morphemes, words, phraseological units, sentences, and texts. These language elements are organized on formal-semantic principles. Speech units include utterances of various lengths where language elements are organized on a semantic-communicative principle. In other words, speech units refer to a specific situation of communication.

Content components are connected with the goal of ELT. The goal determines the content because the content is acquired during the lessons and the result of each lesson depends on the predefined goal. The practical goal of teaching English clarifies how to use some particular language materials in communication, i.e. within which borders and in what capacity. So, the area (topic) of speech is defined. There are three phenomena such as, themes of speech (subjective side of the speech), language sub-skills and skills (procedural side) and language materials (objective side of learning) played a major role for improving the content of teaching English which must be discussed.

Some training specialists think that the content ofFLT includes: a) exercises of different types; b) texts for oral and written work; c) laboratory exercises; d) topical selection of material. The term of “exercise” is usually used with the aim to master

language sub-skills and communicative skills in all speech activities. Exercises are organized as a system or complex directed to development of language sub-skills and skills. Exercises are usually shaped with the language material and task performing to achieve the practical goal. Therefore materials for exercises are taken from the content of teaching. Thus content of teaching is the foundation, source and object of exercises.

The content of FLT involves a dialectical unity of all specifically arranged teaching materials, teaching/learning process, sub-skills and skills, and common essential learning.

Historical survey of FL teaching in the world

Language teaching has been around and changing over the centuries. It is very interesting to look back at the history of FL. It serves us to get to know the different trends and choose the best way to teach the FL.

The history of FL teaching goes back at least to the ancient Greeks. They were interested in what they could learn about mind and the will through language learning. The Romans were probably the first to study a FL officially. They studied Greek, taught by Greek tutors and slaves. Their approach was less philosophical and more practical than that of Greeks.

In Europe before the 16 century, much of the language teaching enclosed teaching Latin to priests. In the 16 and 17 centuries. French was a lingua franca for speaking to foreigners. Mostly court members spoke French, and also it was a required language for travelers, traders and soldiers. French was greatly taught throughout this period, and a study of documents, textbooks, literature indicate that language teachers of that time were considering the same issues that are being considered today. These contained issues about practice versus learning rules and formal study versus informal use.

The status of Latin changed during this period from a living language that learners needed to be able to read, write and speak, to a dead language which was studied as an intellectual exercise. The analysis of the grammar and rhetoric of Classical Latin became the model language teaching between the 17 and 19 centuries, a time when thought about language teaching became fixed in Europe. Emphasis was on learning grammar rules and vocabulary by rote, translations, and practice in writing sample sentences. The translated or written sentences by students were examples of grammatical points and usually had not much relationship to the real world. This method became known as the grammar-translation method. Though some people tried to challenge this type of language education, it was difficult to overcome the attitude that Classical Latin (and to a lesser degree Greek) was the most ideal language and the way it was taught was the model for the way language should be taught. When modern languages were taught as a part of the curriculum, beginning in the 18 century, they were usually taught using the same method as Latin.

The grammar-translation method was the dominant FL teaching method in Europe from the 1840s to the 1940s, and a version of it continues to be widely used in some parts of the world, even today. However, even as early as the mid-19th. theorists were beginning to doubt about the principles behind the grammar-

translation method. Changes were beginning to happen. There was an impressively large demand for ability to speak FL. and various reformers began reconsidering the nature of language and of learning. Among these reformers were two Frenchmen, C.Marcel and F.Gouin, and an Englishman, T.Pendergast. Through their unrelated observations, they concluded that the way that children learned language was relevant to how adults should learn language. Marcel emphasized the significance of understanding meaning in language learning. Pendergast proposed the first structural syllabus. He proposed arranging grammatical structures so that the easiest were taught first. Gouin believed that children learned language through using language for a sequence of related actions. He stressed presenting each item in context and using gestures to supplement verbal meaning.

Though the ideas of these and other reformers had some influence for a time, they didn't become widespread or last long. They were outside of the established educational circles, and the networks of conferences and journals which exist today didn't exist then to spread their ideas.

Nevertheless, in the late 1800s and early 1900s, linguists became interested in the problem of the best way to teach languages. These reformers, as Henry Sweet of England, Wilhelm Victor of Germany, and Paul Passy of France, believed that language teaching should be based on scientific knowledge about language, that it should begin with speaking and expand to other skills, that words and sentences should be presented in context, that grammar should be taught inductively, and that translation should, for the most part, be avoided. These ideas spread, and were consolidated in what became known as the Direct method, first of the natural methods. The Direct method became popular in language schools, but it was not very practical with larger classes or in public schools.

In the early to mid-1900s developments in other fields such as psychology, behaviorism has had a great effect on language teaching resulting in the audio-lingual method. The audio-lingual method has students listen to or view tapes of language models acting in situations. Students practice with variety of drills, and their instructor emphasizes the use of the target language at all times. The audio-lingual method was used by the United States Army for «crash» instruction in FL during World War II. Despite the documented success of these programs, they are no longer common.

In the years following World War II, great changes took place that influenced on language teaching and learning. Language diversity greatly increased so there were more languages to learn.

Expansion of schooling meant that language learning was no longer the privileged of the elite but something necessary for widening range of people. More opportunities for international travel and business and international social and cultural exchanges increased the demand for language learning. As a result, renewed efforts were made in the 1950s and 1960s to 1) use new technology (e.g., tape recorders, radios, TV and computers) effectively in language teaching, 2) explore new educational models (e.g., bilingual education, individualized instruction, etc.) and 3) establish methodological innovations (audio-lingual method). Yet, the desired increase in the effectiveness of language education didn't

come about, and some of the theoretical footings of the developments were called into issue.

The start of the mid-1960s is distinguished by a range of theoretical challenges to the audio-lingual method. Linguist Noam Chomsky challenged the behaviorist model of language learning. He proposed a theory called Transformational Generative Grammar, as per which learners do not acquire an endless list of rules but limited set of transformations which can be used over and over again, (e.g., a sentence is changed from affirmative to a negative sentence by adding not and the auxiliary verb.) so that the language learner can form big number of sentences.

Other theorists have also proposed ideas influencing language teaching. Stephen Krashen, for example, studied the way that children learn language and applied it to adult language learning. He proposed the Input Hypothesis, which states that language is acquired by using comprehensible input (the language that one hears in the environment) which is slightly beyond the learners' present proficiency.

There have been big developments since the early 1970s. Individualized instruction, development, of communicative approach, more humanistic approach to language learning and finally a greater stress on authenticity in language learning has become more required. Some «new methods» have gained followings.

Communicative language teaching (CLT) is an approach to the teaching languages that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language. Despite a number of criticisms, it continues to be popular, particularly in Europe, where constructivist views on language learning and education in general dominate academic discourse.

Language immersion puts students in a situation where they must use a FL, whether or not they know it. This creates fluency, but not accuracy of usage. French-language immersion programs are common in Canada in the state school system as part of the drive towards bilingualism.

Minimalist/Methodologist approach (Paul Rowe's minimalist/ Methodologist approach) is underpinned with Paul Nation's three actions of successful ESL (English as a second language) teachers. Initially it was written specifically for unqualified, inexperienced people teaching in EFL (English as FL) situations. Still experienced language teachers are also responding positively to its simplicity. Language items are usually provided using flashcards. There is a focus on language-in-context and multi-functional practices.

Directed practice has students repeat phrases. This method is used by US diplomatic courses. It can quickly provide phrasebook- type knowledge of the language. Within these limits, the student's usage is accurate and precise. Conversely the student's choice of what to say is not flexible.

Learning by teaching is a widespread method in Germany (Jean-Pol Martin). The students take the teacher's role and teach their peers. An important target is developing web-sensibility.

The Pimsleur language learning system is based on the research of and model programs developed by American language teacher Paul Pimsleur. Over a dozen

audio-tape programs now exist to teach various languages using the Pimsleur Method.

Several methodologies that emphasize understanding language in order to learn, rather than producing it, exist as varieties of the comprehension approach. These include Total Physical Response and the natural approach of Steven Krashen and Tracy D. Terrell.

The Silent Way is a discovery learning approach, proposed by Galeb Gattegno in the 50s of the last century. It is often considered to be one of the humanistic approaches. It is called The Silent Way because the teacher is usually silent, leaving room for students to talk and explore the language. It is often associated with Cuisenaire rods and wall charts where words are colour-coded; each phoneme a different colour.

Besides voluminous methods and approaches there are certain learning strategies that play big role in language teaching/learning.

Code switching, i.e. changing between languages at some point in a sentence or utterance, is commonly used communication strategy among language learners and bilinguals. While traditional methods of formal instruction often discourage code switching, students, especially those placed in a language immersion situation, often use it. If viewed as a learning strategy, wherein the student uses the target language for any element of an utterance that they are unable to produce in the target language, then it has the advantages that it encourages fluency development and motivation and a sense of accomplishment by enabling the student to discuss topics of interest to him or her early in the learning process - before requisite vocabulary has been memorized.

Blended learning combines face-to-face teaching with distance education, frequently electronic, either computer-based or web-based. It has been a major growth point in the ELT (English language Teaching) industry over the last two decades.

Some people, yet, use the phrase «Blended Learning» to refer to learning taking place while focus is on other activities. For example, playing a card game that requires calling for cards may allow blended learning of numbers (1 to 10). Private tutoring, i.e. tutoring by a native speaker can be one of the most effective ways of learning. However, it requires a skilled, motivated native tutor, which can be a rare, expensive commodity. That tutor may draw on one or several of the above methods.

Besides proposed methods and approaches through history, there are also some other means that broaden the choice of learning FL like language study holidays, language education on the internet, etc.

An increasing number of people are now combining holidays with language study in the native country. This enables the student to experience the target culture by meeting local people. Such a holiday often combines formal lessons, cultural excursions, leisure activities and homestay, perhaps with time to travel in the country afterwards. Language study holidays are popular across Europe due to the ease of transportation and to the small geographical distances. Many individuals travel to the UK alone to learn English.

The internet has emerged as a powerful medium to teach and learn FLs which provides a beneficial supplement to real world language schooling. Websites provide language exchange, i.e. two users with complementary language skills, e.g., a native English speaker and a native Chinese speaker who are eager to learn one another's language from different countries, can teach each other their languages.

There are a number of portals that offer language content, some in interactive form. Content typically comprises phrases with translation in multiple languages, text speech engines, learning activities such as quizzes or puzzles based on language concepts for free.

GLOSSARIY

A	отличная, высшая оценка (UK, US) (возможные категории A, A-, A=)	a'lo. yuqori baho (UK, US) (toifalari A, A-, A=)
abbreviation	сокращение	qisqartma
ability	способность	qobiliyat
ABC	алфавит	alfavit
abridged	сокращенный, краткое	qisqartirilgan, qisqa
absorb	поглощать, впитывать (знания)	(bilimni) egallamoq, yutmoq
abstract	резюме; отрывок из книги;отвлеченное понятие	rezyume, mavhum
abstraction	абстракция	mavhumot, xayoliy, mavhum narsa
academic	учебный; академический	akademik; ta'limga oid
academic adviser	научный консультант	ilmiy maslahatchi
acceleration	акселерация, скорость обучения или развития	akseleratsiya, o'qish yoki rivojlanish tezligi
accent	акцент	aksent; talaffuzga oid
accomplish	выполнять, достигать совершенства	bajarmoq, mukammalikka erishmoq
accordance	соответствие	moslik
acculturation	аккультурация	akkulturatsiya
accuracy	правильность	to'g'rilik, aniqlik
achievement	успеваемость, обученность	o'zlashtirish, yutuq
acknowledge	подтверждать, признавать	tasdiqlamoq, tan olmoq
acoustic	акустик, звуковой	akustik, ovozli
acquire	приобретать	egallamoq
acquaintance	знакомство	tanishuv
acquisition	владение	egallash
act	акт	akt, ijro
action	действие, движение	harakat, faoliyat
activate	активировать	faollashtirmoq

active	активный	aktiv, faol
activization	активизация	faollashtirish
actualization	актуализация	aktualizatsiya
ada't	адаптировать	moslash(tir)ish
ada'tation	адаптация	moslash(tir)ish
ada'tive	адаптивная (гибкая)	moslashuvchan dastur
'rogram(me)	программа	
administrate	управлять	boshqarmoq
admission	вступительный	kirish
advance	упреждение,	oldindan chorasini ko'rish
advanced	продвинутый	ilg'or
advancement	продвижение	Ilgarilash
affixation	аффиксация	Affiksatsiya
aim	цель	maqсад, tasavvuridagi natija
A-level	повышенный уровень (UK)	yuqori daraja (UK)
algorithm	алгоритм	Algoritm
algorithmization	алгоритмизация	algoritmizatsiya, algoritm lash
al'habet	алфавит	Alfavit
alternative	альтернативный	Alternative
altruism	альтруизм	Altruism
analogy	аналогия	moslik, monandlik, munosiblik
analysis	анализ	analiz, tahlil
analytic	аналитический	analitik, tahliliy
analytic-synthetic	аналитико	analitik-sintetik
analyze	анализировать	tahlil qilmoq
analyzed	анализированный	Tahliliy
analyzer	анализатор	Analizator
annotation	аннотация	annotatsiya, asar haqida qisqacha
announce	объявлять	bildirmoq, e'lon qilmoq
answer	ответ	Javob
antici'ation	антиципация	antisi'atsiya, harakat natijasini,
antonym	антоним	antonim
anxiety	беспокойство	bezovtalik
a''erce'tion	апперцепция	a''erse'siya, idrokning avvalgi
a''licant	заявитель, кандидат	ariza beruvchi
a''lication	заявление	ariza
a''lied linguistics	прикладная	amaliy tilshunoslik
a''rentice	ученик, подмастерье	o'quvchi, shogird
a''roach	подход	yondashuv, til o'rgatish yondashuvlari
a''ro'riacy	соответствие	moslik
a''roximation	аппроксимация	a''roksimatsiya,
a''titude	пригодность к деятельности	faoliyatga iqtidor, qobiliyat
articulating	артикуляционный	artikulatsiyga oid
articulation	артикуляция	artikulatsiya
artificial	искусственный	sun'iy
arts	гуманитарные науки; классические	gumanitar fanlar
ask	спрашивать	so'ramoq
assessment	оценка	baholash
assign	поручать, давать задание	to'shiriq/vazifa bermoq
assignment	задание	vazifa, to'shiriq
assimilate	ассимилировать,	o'zlashtirmoq,

association	ассоциация	assotsiatsiya
associative	ассоциативный	assotsiativ
assum'tion	предположение	tahmin
attainment	успеваемость,	o'zlashtirishlik,
attendance	посещение	davomat
attention	внимание	diqqat
attention s'an	объем/время внимания	diqqat hajmi/muddati
attitude	отношение	munosabat
auding	аудирование	tinglab tushunish
audio	аудио	audio
audio-aids	аудиоматериалы	audiomateriallar
audio-exercise	аудиоупражнение	audiomashq
audio information	аудиоинформация	audioaxborot
audio-lingual	аудиолингвальный	audiolingval
audiolingualism	аудиолингвализм	audiolingvalizm
audio-materials	аудиоматериалы	audiomateriallar
audio-news	аудионовости	audioxabar
audio-text	аудиотекст	audiomatn, audiotekst
audio-visual	аудиовизуал	audiovizual
audition	слух; слушание, аудирование	eshitish; tinglash
auditive	аудитив	auditiv, tinglashga mo'ljallangan
auditor	аудитор, слушатель	auditor, tinglovchi
auditorium	аудитория	auditoriya
auditory	слухопроизноситель	eshitib talaffuz qilishga oid
aural	слуховой	eshitishga oid
authentic	аутентичный	asl, autentik
author	автор	muallif
automaticity	автоматизм	avtomatizm
automatism	автоматизм	avtomatizm
automatization	автоматизация	avtomatlashuv
autonomous	самостоятельное	mustaqil
autosuggestion	самовнушение	ixlos qilish, ko'ngilga tugish
aware: to be ~	знать, быть осведомленным	bilmoq, bohabar bo'lmoq
B	хорошая или удовлетворительная	yaxshi yoki qoniqarli baho (UK, US)
baccalaureate	бакалавриат	bakalavriat
bachelor	бакалавр	bakalavr
barrier	барьер	tafovut, to'siq
base	база	baza, asos
basic	базовый	asosiy
basic course	основной учебный курс или	asosiy o'quv kursi yoki fani
be based	основываться	tayanmoq
behaviorism	бихевиоризм	bixeviorizm
biculturalism	бикультурность	ikkimadaniyatlik
bilingual	билингв, двуязычный	zulli'nayn, bilingv, ikki tilli,
book	книга	kitob
bottom-u'	(подход)снизу вверх	'astdan te'aga yondashuvi
brainstorming	мозговая атака	aqliy hujum
branched	разветвленная	tarmoqli (dastur)
broadcast	радиопередача	radio eshittirish
C	удовлетворительная, или менее чем	qoniqarli, yoki qoniqarsizroq baho (UK,
	оценка (UK, US), (возможные	C-, C=)

calendar	календарь	kalendar
calligra'hy	чистописание,	husnixat, kalligrafiya
card	карточка	qalin qog'ozdan kesilgan varaqcha
case	событие	hodisa
case-study	кейс-стади, методика ситуативного	keys-stadi, vaziyatli o'qitish metodikasi
case-technology	кейс-технология	keys-texnologiya, vaziyatli o'qitish
chat	болтать, разговаривать	chaqchaqlashmoq,
CEFR (Common Euro'ean	Общеввропейские компетенции	umumyevro'e tilni egallash
centric	центрированный	Markazlashgan
certificate	сертификат	Sertifikat
certification	сертификационный	Sertifikatlashtiruvchi
chant	петь	qo'shiq aytmoq
chorus	хор	jo'r bo'lish
circumlocution	многоречивость	ko'ga'irish, ezmalik
citation	цитата	iqtibos
classes	занятие, урок	mashg'ulot
classification	классификация	tasnif, guruhlash, turlarga ajratish,
class work	классная работа	sinf ishi
cliche	клише	klishe
climate	климат	muhit
cloze-test	клоуз-тест, тест для определения	klouz-test, matni o'qish va mazmunini
clues	ключевой	kalit, kalit so'zlar yoki stimullar
cluster	кластерный	klasterga oid
coach	репетитор	re'etitor
coaching	коучинг	imtihonga tayyorlash
code	код	kod, shartli belgi
cognate	однокоренной	yaqin, bir-biriga bog'langan
cognitive	когнитивный,	bilishga oid, bildiradigan
cognitivism	когнитивизм	kognitivizm
cognizant	когнизант	kognizant, bilimdon, oqil, omilkor
coherence	слаженность	butunlik, o'zaro bog'liqlik
collaborate	сотрудничать	hamkorlik qilmoq
collocation	словосочетание	so'z birikmasi
colloquial	разговорный	so'zlashuvga oid
communicant	собеседник	suhbatdosh, o'zaro so'zlashuvchi ikki
communication	коммуникация	kommunikatsiya, nutqiy aloqa, fikr
communicative	коммуникативный	kommunikativ,
com'arative	компаративный,	kom'arativ, qiyosiy
com'are	сравнивать,	qiyoslamq,
	сопоставлять	taqqoslamq,
com'etence	компетенция	kom'etensiya
com'etition	олимпиада, конкурс	olim'iada, musobaqa, konkurs, ko'rik,
com'ile	составлять (учебник, пособие)	(darslik, qo'llanma) tuzmoq
com'lete	полный, совершенный	mukammal, to'liq
com'letion	упражнение на дополнение	qo'shimcha uchun mashq
com'lex	комплекс	kom'leks, majmua
com'onent	компонент	kom'onent, tarkib, qism, tarkibiy qism
com'ose	составлять, составить	tuzmoq
com'rehend	понимать; охватывать содержание	tushunmoq; mazmunni anglamoq
com'ression	компрессия	kom'ressiya,
com'ulsory	обязательный	majburiy

com`uter	компьютер	kom`yuter, elektr hisoblash mashinasi
com`uter-assisted	с помощью компьютера	kom`yuter yordamida
concentre	концентрироваться	diqqat, e`tiborni bir joyga qaratmoq
concentric	концентрический	konsentrik
concentrism	концентризм	konsentrizm
conce`pt	концепт	konse`pt
conce`tion	концепция	konse`siya, ilmiy g`oya(lar)
concise	сжатый, краткий	qisqa, qisqartirilgan, siqilgan
condition	условие	sharoit, holat, vaziyat
confidence	уверенность	ishonch
connotation	коннотация	so`zning majoziy ma`nosi
conscious	сознательный	ongli
conscious- com`arative: ~	сознательно-	ongli-qiyosiy metod
consciousness	сознание,	ong, onglilik
conscious- `ractical: ~ method	сознательнопрактический метод	ongli-amaliy metod
constant	постоянный	doimiy
consultation	консультация	konsultatsiya, o`quvchilarga
contact	контакт	kontakt, o`zaro aloqada bo`lmoq
contem`orary	современный	zamonaviy
content	содержание	mazmun, tarkib
content of teaching grammar	содержание обучения грамматики	grammatikani o`rgatish mazmuni
content of teaching `ronunciation	содержание обучения	talaffuzni o`rgatish mazmuni (TO`M)
content of teaching vocabulary	содержание обучение лексике	leksikani o`rgatish mazmuni (LO`M)
contest	конкурс, олимпиада	olim`iada, musobaqa, konkurs, ko`rik
context	контекст	kontekst, so`z, so`z birikmasi, ibora og`zaki nutq `archasi
contextual	контекстуальный	kontekstual, kontekst bilan bog`liq
contrastive	контрастивный	kontrastiv
control	контроль	nazorat, tekshiruv, kontrol
control `anel	пульт	`ult
conversation	разговор	suhbat, so`zlashish, musohada, guring
correction	исправление (ошибки); поправка	(xato) to`g`rilash; tuzatish
corrective: ~ course	коррективный курс	korrektiv kurs
correlation	корреляция	korrelyatsiya, chet til ta`limi
counselling	метод общины	jamoaviy til o`rganish metodi
country study	страноведение	mamlakatshunoslik
course	курс	kurs
cramming	зубрёжка	(tushunmasdan) yod olish
creative	творческий,	ijodiy, ijodkor
creativity	креативность,	ijod, ijodkorlik
criterion (<i>z</i> -ia)	критерий	mezon, o`lchov, `rinsi`
critical	критический	tanqidiy
C-test	разновидность клоуз- теста	klouz-test turlaridan biri
cues	опоры, опоры-стимулы	tayanch turtki
culture	культура	madaniyat
culture shock	культурный шок	madaniy zarba
culturology	культурология	madaniyatshunoslik
cumulative	кумулятивный	kumulativ
cybernetics	кибернетика	kibernetika, axborotni olish, saqlash,
cyclicity	цикличность	sikllilik, davrlilik
D	неудовлетворительная оценка (UK,	C-, C= (UK, US) toifalariga yaqin

data (<i>sing.</i> - datum)	данные, факты	ma'lumotlar, dalillar
data driven learning (DDL)	обучение с помощью базы данных	ma'lumotlar asosida o'qitish
deaf-and-dumb	сурдопедагогика	surdo'edagogika
deautomatization	деавтоматизация	deavtomatizatsiya
decode	декодировать	to'ib o'qimoq
deduction	дедукция	deduktsiya
deductive	дедуктивный	deduktiv
deficit	недочёты	kamchiliklar
definition	определение	ta'rif, defnitsiya
demonstration	демонстрация	namoyish,
descri'tive	описательная	tasviriy grammatika
develo'	развивать	rivojlan(tir)moq
develo'ing	развивающий	rivojlantiruvchi
diagnostic test	диагностический тест	diagnostik test, dastlabki sinov
dialogic	диалогический	dialogik
dialogue	диалог	juftnutq, dialog, suhbat
didactic	дидактический	didaktik
didactics	дидактика, теория образования	ta'limshunoslik, didaktika, ta'lim
differenciate	дифференцировать	farqlamoq, tabaqalamoq
differentiation	дифференциация	tabaqalash,
difficult	трудный	qiyin, mushkul, murakkab
difficulty	трудность	qiyinchilik, lisoniy tafovut hosilasi
dictate	диктовать	tinglovchi yozib olishi uchun ovoz
dictation	диктант	diktant
direct: ~ method	прямой метод	to'g'ri metod
direction	направление, указание, установка	ko'rsatma, yo'riq
di'loma	диплом	di'lom
disci'line	поведение учащихся	o'quvchi hulqi
discourse	дискурс	diskurs, nutqiy vaziyatdagi matn
discursive	дискурсивный	diskursiv
distinction	различие, отличие, разница	farq
distract	отвлекать	chalg'itmoq
distribution	организация	taqsimot, distributsiya, taqsimlash,
distributive	распределительный	taqsimlovchi
draft	черновик	qoralama
dramatization	инсценировка	inssenirovka, nasriy yoki she'riy asarni
drill	тренировка	g'ayrisha'uriy mashq
drilling	зарядка	mashq, shug'ullanish
durability	прочность	mustahkamlik
dynamic	динамический	dinamik
easy	легкий	oson, o'zlashtirish uchun kam kuch
education	образование,	ta'lim, o'qitish, o'rgatish, maorif,
educational	образовательный	ta'limiy, ta'limga oid
educator	учитель	o'qituvchi, muallim, domla, ta'lim-
efficiency	работоспособность	ish (ishlash) qobiliyati, layoqati
egocentrism	эгоцентризм	egosentrizm, o'ta ketgan manmanlik
electicism	электический подход	elektik yondashuv (aralash metod)
elective	элективный (предмет, курс,	qo'shimcha, tanlov (fan, darslik)
elicitation/	приём, используемый для	nutqiy-fikriy faoliyat o'rgatish usuli
emotion	эмоция	tuyg'u, kechinma
environment	атмосфера	atmosfera, muhit

e'i-'rojector	эпипроектор	svetotexnik ta'lim vositalaridan biri
e'istemology	гносология	gnoseologiya (bilish nazariyasi)
e'istolary	эпистолярный	e'istolar, maktubiy, xatga oid
ergonomics	эргономика	ergonomika
error	(грубая) ошибка	(qo'ol) xato, nutqda til materialini oqibati
erudition	эрудиция	bilimdonlik
essay	изложение	insho (esse)
ethno'sychology	этнопсихология	etno'sixologiya
etiquette	этикет	etiket, odob
etude	этюд	etyud, sun'iy namuna
etymology	этимология	etimologiya
Euro'ean language 'ortfolio	европейский языковой портфель	yevro'a lisoniy 'ortfel
exam	экзамен, проверка	sinov. imtihon
exercise	упражнение	mashq, chet tilda bajariladigan o'quv
ex'ansion	упражнение на расширение	kengaytirish uchun mashq
ex'perience	опыт	tajriba
ex'eriment	эксперимент	eks'eriment, tajriba
ex'erimental	экспериментальный	eks'erimental
ex'lain	объяснять	tushuntirmoq
ex'press-method	экспресс-метод	eks'res-metodi
ex'osition	экспозиция	ko'rgazma
ex'ository	описательный,	tasvirlovchi, izohlovchi
extensive	экстенсивный	ekstensiv
exteriorization	экстериоризация	eksteriorizatsiya (tashqi harakat)
exteriorization of s'eech	экстериоризация речи	tashqi nutq (og'zaki, yozma)
extralinguistical	экстралингвисти-	ekstralingvistik
extraversion	экстраверсия	ekstraversiya, introversiyaga zid
extravert	экстраверт	ekstravert, muloqotchan
facilitation	фасилитация	fasilitatsiya, yordam, yengillashtirish
facilitator	посредник	yordamchi
facultative	факультативный	fakultativ (majburiy bo'Imagan)
filling	заполнение	to'ldirish
film	фильм	film
film exercise	киноупражнение	kinomashq, kino namoyish qilib
film fragment	кинокадр	kinokadr, kino'archa, kinofragment
film lesson	киноурок	kinodars
filmstri's	диафильм	diafilm
final	заключительный	yakuniy
flanelegra'h	фланелеграф	flanelegraf
fluency	беглость	ravonlik
fluent	свободный	ravon
foreign (<i>adj.</i>) ~ language	иностраннй иностранный язык	ajnabiy, xorijiy, chet til; maktabda
foreign language teacher's	портфель учителя иностранного	chetl til o'qituvchisi 'ortfoliosi
foreigner	иностранец	xorijzabon, horijlik, chet ellik
form	форма	forma, shakl
formal	формальный	formal, rasmiy
formation	формирование	shakllanish
forming	формирующий	shakllantiruvchi
forum	форум	forum
fossilization	фоссилизация	fossilizasiya

frontal	фронтальный	frontal, yo''asiga, ommaviy
function	функция	qo'llanilish
functional	функциональный	funksional
gender	" гендерный	gender, jinsga oid
general	общее	umumiy
generalization	обобщение	umumlashma, qoida, mavhumot, sodda
generalize	обобщать	umumlashtirmoq
genetic	генетический	genetik, irsiy
gestalt-style	гештальт-стиль (подход от общего	gestalt-uslub (umumiydan hususiyga
gesture	жест, мимика	imo-ishora
global	глобальный	global (ommaviy)
gnoseology	гносология	gnoseologiya (bilish nazariyasi)
goal	цель	maqsad
grade	класс	sinf, yagona o'quv dasturi bo'yicha
graduated	градуированный	ma'lumotli
grammar	грамматика,	grammatika, grammatik
gra'heme	графема	grafema
gra'hic (<i>adj.</i>)	графический	grafik
gra'hic (<i>n.</i>)	графика	grafika
grou' (<i>n.</i>)	группа	guruh, tabaqa, toifa
grou' (<i>adj.</i>)	групповой	guruhiy
grou'ing	группирование	guruhlash
guesswork	догадки	to'qirlikka oid mashq
guidance	руководство, программа, пособие,	dasturamal, qo'llanma, dastur, darslik
	Учебник	
handbook	учебное пособие, руководство	qo'llanma, dasturamal
handout	раздаточный	tarqatma
handwriting	Почерк	husnixat
hear	Слышать	eshitmoq
hearing	Слуховой	eshituv
hesitation	хезитация	ikkilanish
heuristic	эвристический	evristikaga oid, evristik
hierarchy	иерархия	iyerarxiya (tadrij)
historical	исторический	tarixiy
homework	домашнее задание	uy vazifasi
home reading	домашнее чтение	uyda o'qish uchun vazifa
homogra'h	омограф	omograf, yozuvda o'xshash, biroq turli
homonym	омоним	omonim, shakldosh, ma'nodosh
homo'hone	омофон	omofon, aytilishda obxshash, ma'nosi
hy'eractivity	гиперактивность	o'ta faollik
hy'no'edia	гипнопедия	gi'no'ediya
i-conce'tion	концепт -я	men - konse'ti
idea	идея, представление	g'oya, fikr
idiom	идиома	idioma
illustration	иллюстрация	rasm, surat
imitate	имитировать	taqlid qilmoq
imitation	имитация	imitatsiya (taqlid)
imitative	имитативный	taqlidiy
immanent	имманентный	bevosita (immanent)
im'lementation	выполнение	bajarish
im'licit	имплицитный,	yashirin, nazarda tutiladigan,

im'rinting	импринтинг,	taasurot, (xotirada) muxrianish
im'rovment (of 'rofessional	повышение	(malaka) oshirish
im'rovving	совершенствующий	takomillashtiruvchi
im'rovisation	импровизация	badiha
im'rovised	импровизированная, случайная	tayyorlanmagan (nutq)
inde'endent	самостоятельный	mustaqil
indicative (mood)	изъявительное	aniq (nisbat)
individual	индивидуал	individual (shaxsiy)
individualization	индивидуализация	shaxsga bog'liqlik
induction	индукция	induksiya
inductive	индуктивный	induktiv
influence	влияние	ta'sir
information	информация	axborot (informatsiya)
informational	информационный	axborotga oid
informative	информативный	informativ
initial	начальный, пороговый	dastlabki, boshlang'ich
initiative	инициативный	erkin (nutq)
insistence	настойчивость	tirishqoqlik, turg'unlik
ins'iration	поощрение	rag'bat
integral	интегральный, целый, цельный,	butun, ajralmas, yaxlit
integrated	интегрированный	butun yaxlit xolda
integrative	интегративный	umumlashtiruvchi, bir butun qiluvchi
integrity	целостность	butunlik, yaxlitlik
integration	интеграция	yaxlitlash
intellect	интеллект	intellekt, aql
intellectual	интеллектуальный	intellektual, aqliy
intensification	интенсификация	jadallashtirish,
intensify	интенсировать	faollishtirmoq
intensive	интенсивный	judal
intention	намерение	niyat, istak
interaction	интеракция	o'zaro ta'sir
interactive	интерактивный	interaktiv
interest	интерес	qiziqish
intercultural	межкультурный	madaniyatlararo
interface	интерфейс	o'zaro bog'lanish
interference	интерференция	interferensiya, salbiy ta'sir
interferential	интерференционный	interferensiyaga oid
interiorization	интериоризация	interiorizatsiya, ichki harakat
interlingua	язык-посредник	vosita tili
interlocutor	собеседник	suhbatdosh
international	интернациональный	xalqaro, baynalmilal
international friendshi' club	международный клуб дружбы	baynalmilal do'stlik klubi (XDK)
internationalism	интернационализм	internatsionalizm (xalqaro birdamlik)
internet	интернет	internet
interval	интервал; промежуток	oraliq; tanaffus
interview	интервью	intervyu, mushohada
in-textual	притекстовые	matn-o'qish (mashqlari)
intonation	интонация	intonatsiya, ohang
introduction	введение	kirish
intros'ection	самонаблюдение	o'z-o'zini kuzatish
introversion	интроверсия, сосредоточенность на	introversiya, o'ziga berilganlik

introvert	^ интроверт	kamga', tortinchoq
intuitive	интуитивный	intuitiv
intuition	интуиция	ichki his, sezgirlik
issue	проблема	masala
jigsaw:	мозаика;	mozaika;
~ activities	упражнения для обмена	ma'lumot almashinish uchun "mozaika"
judgement	суждение	hukm
keyword	ключевое/ опорное слово	tayanch, til o'rganishga yordam
kinesthetic	кинестетик	kinestetik, harakatga oid
know	знать	bilmoq
knowledge	знание	bilim
lab . = laboratory	лаборатория	laboratoriya
laboratory	лаборатория	laboratoriya
lacuna	лакуна	qiyoslanayotgan tillarning birida mos
language	язык	til, lison
language 'ortfolio	языковой портфель	lisoniy 'ortfolio
latent	скрытый, латентный	latent, so'zning xotirada saqlanish
layout	расположение	joylashuv, joylashish tartibi
learner-centred	лично	o'quvchiga
lecture	лекция	leksiya, oily o'quv yurtida tegishli
lesson	урок	mashg'ulot, dars, saboq
letter	буква; письмо	harf; xat
lexical	лексический	leksikaga oid
lexicon	лексикон, толковый словарь	izohli lug'at
linear syllabus	программа линейного типа	takrorlanmas turdagi dastur
linguodidactics	лингводидактика	lingvodidaktika, til ta'limshunosligi
linguo-country	лингвострановедение	lingvomamlakatshu-
linguoculturology	лингвокультурология	lingvakulturologiya,
lingual	лингвистический	lisoniy, tilga oid
linguo'hysiology	лингвофизиология	lingvofiziologiya, nutq fiziologiyasi
linguo'sychology	лингвопсихология	lingvopsixologiya, til o'rgatish
linguostylistics	лингвостилистика	lingvistilistika
linguotechnology	лингвотехнология	lingvotexnologiya
linguist	лингвист, языковед	tilshunos
linguistic	лингвистический	filologik
linguistics	лингвистика	tilshunoslik
linked	прикрепленный	bog'langan (til hodisasi)
linking	прикрепляемый	bog'lanuvchi (unli oldi o'qiladigan [r])
listening	понимание на слух	tinglab tushunish
literal	буквальный	so'zma-so'z
literary	литературный	adabiy
live	живой	jonli
localization	локализация	mahalliy sharoitga moslashtirish
logics	логика	mantiq (fan)
macro text	макротекст	makromatn
master	магистр	magistr
master-class	мастер-класс	malakali mutaxassis darsi
material	материал	material
means	средство	vosita
mechanic	механический	mexanik (ong

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